

**THE EXPERIENCE OF THE STUDY CYCLE AS A TRAINING
ACTIVITY BY PIBID - CAP/UERN LITERACY**

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7523520

Kaliane Valdemiro dos Santos

*Undergraduate student of the Pedagogy course at the Advanced Campus of Patu –
CAP/UERN.*

Email: kaly177paturn@gmail.com

Lorena Mariele da Silva Galdino

*Undergraduate student of the Pedagogy course at the Advanced Campus of Patu –
CAP/UERN. Email: lorenamariele.lm@gmail.com*

Rubens Mateus Bezerra de Lucena

*Graduating from the Pedagogy course at the Advanced Campus of Patu –
CAP/UERN.*

Email: rubens.mateus20@gmail.com

Italo Jose Sales Marques

*Graduating from the Pedagogy course at the Advanced Campus of Patu –
CAP/UERN.*

E-mail: italomarques@alu.uern.br

Iure Coutre Gurgel

Professor of the Pedagogy course at the Advanced Campus of Patu - CAP/UERN.

Email: yurecoutre@yahoo.com.br

Abstract: This article presents a discussion about the experiences with the cycle of studies lived with undergraduates of the Pedagogy course - Advanced Campus of Patu - CAP of the State University of Rio Grande do Norte - UERN, who work in the Institutional Program of Initiation Scholarships to Teaching - PIBID of the Literacy subproject. The objective is to reflect on the contributions of study cycles as a formative and reflective activity for undergraduates who are members of PIBID from the perspective of initiation to teaching, as

well as, for supervising teachers, carried out in this pandemic context, remotely, emphasizing the importance of theoretical studies carried out during the meetings as essential activities to (re)think the teaching practice through reflexivity and pedagogical practice. As a theoretical foundation, we rely on the studies of: BRASIL (2018), TARDIF; LESSARD (2005), ANDRÉ (2010), among others. The methodology developed is characterized as research with a qualitative, empirical approach, in which we carried out a literature review and documentary research. The research subjects were the two supervising teachers participating in the subproject. For data collection, we applied a questionnaire via WhatsApp. The research results point to a relevant factor of the cycle, being the act of contributing to the other, whether a student or a teacher. From the study cycles, we understand that the moments of studies and discussions about the themes worked on provided the construction of new learning, in which each one has speeches and practices that can and will contribute both to the training and professional growth of the other.

Keywords: teaching learning. study cycles. pibid-literacy.

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, education has been going through a process of transitions and transformations. Basically 150 years ago, in the middle of the 19th century, a new school model spread and consolidated throughout the world, which, despite so much criticism and resistance, has become accepted nowadays.

In the time of one generation, over the next 20 or 30 years, we will witness a complex metamorphosis of the school (Nóvoa, 2021), that is, a change in its form. It is a change of course, a new origin (Morin, 2011), that is, the school as a space of social, cultural and educational transformation, has been undergoing profound transformations within society, linked to this, it must also be a space that provides the construction and mediation of knowledge necessary for the operationalization of the teaching and learning process in an interdisciplinary and collaborative perspective, based on lived experiences, the exchange of knowledge and formative and dialogical activities that have been carried out in recent years, in view of the specific characteristics of this new school model that have been emerging in the current scenario.

With that, through all these transformations, it is worth highlighting the importance of training programs, as opportunities to learn from practice, reflection and integration between subjects, as well as through incentives in the initial training of teaching students in courses of degrees, promoted through educational public policies, such as PIBID, which aim to insert students in the "ground" of the basic network school to experience the experience of pedagogical practice, thus aiming at the partnership between school and university .

Unfortunately, due to the current pandemic scenario, it was not possible for us to develop all the actions planned by the subproject in practice, within the classrooms, thus culminating in the immersion of remote teaching, so, from there, a new format of program meetings, which we call formative study cycles, carried out remotely on themes related to the theme proposed by the project developed by CAP/UERN, more precisely by the literacy subproject.

In this thinking, this article aims to reflect on the contributions of study cycles as a teaching activity with PIBID undergraduates from the perspective of initiation into teaching, carried out in this pandemic context remotely, through synchronous and asynchronous meetings.

Next, we will address some notes of authors who highlight the references about the importance of PIBID in the process of initial teacher training, for this, we will present some topics related to the knowledge of PIBID - CAP/UERN Literacy and the experience with the study cycles, covering, therefore, with the participation of teachers from the municipal basic network of the city of Patu/RN, who in this edition 2020 to 2022 are supervisory teachers of the program.

GETTING TO KNOW PIBID CAP/UERN LITERACY

At the outset, it is important to briefly contextualize the purpose of PIBID. PIBID is one of the policy initiatives on initial teacher training by the Ministry of Education-MEC, which aims to provide students of degree courses from different higher education institutions, in the first half of the course, with a practical approach in school spaces of public networks of Basic Education and with the context in which both are inserted. The program aims, with this approximation, to encourage undergraduates, from the beginning of their training, to make observations and reflections on professional practice in the daily life of schools.

PIBID makes available a quota of monthly scholarships to its members and also has student volunteers in all subprojects. In addition to the undergraduates participating in the subproject, we have the subproject coordinator, in this case, the university professor and the supervisors, in which they are the Basic Education teachers of the school selected, equally, by the program.

After a brief contextualization, we continue with the study of the CAP/UERN Literacy subproject. Our subproject has as participants, the coordinator and professor of the selected institution, the graduates of the Pedagogy course (CAP/UERN), these being among scholarship holders and volunteers, as well as supervisors and teachers of Basic Education. The prioritized

public schools were from the city of Patu/RN, being from the initial years, in this case, a 2nd year class, and from Messias Targino/RN, being from the area of Early Childhood Education. The Literacy subproject aims to,

- Foster initiation into teaching, contributing to the improvement of teacher training at a higher level and to improving the quality of public Basic Education in the municipality of Patu/RN; - Contribute to improving the literacy rates of students in the early years; - Favor the inclusion of UERN Pedagogy undergraduates in the day-to-day activities of educational institutions, with the aim of realizing the movement produced there and developing interdisciplinary intervention strategies, of a methodological, technological and practical nature, that minimize/close sociocultural problem-situations and educational that hinder advances in the processes of teaching, learning and teaching-learning; - To provide those involved in the PIBID Project (graduates and professors of Pedagogy, supervising professors) with the study and scientific knowledge in the sphere of literacy, literacy and numeracy, based on the principles of cognitive sciences (cognitive psychology and cognitive neuroscience); - Contribute with the eradication of childhood illiteracy by investing in school/educational practices as advocated by the National Literacy Policy/PNA and the National Common Curricular Base/BNCC. (CAP/UERN, 2020)

We seek to develop a subproject that envisages the construction of an integrative, dynamic and collaborative work, through the planning, studies and mediations of the coordinator. That is, as graduates of the Pedagogy course and with the objective of exercising the teaching profession, we aim for these practices, experienced from the program, to allow us to contribute to the improvement both during our training/preparation for teaching learning, and to promote progress in the quality of teaching and learning at the subproject's partner schools. In addition, we studied the curriculum documents, consisting of the National Curricular Guidelines - DCNs (BRASIL, 2017), which are responsible for guiding the curriculum planning of Basic Education networks and teaching units, and the National Common Curricular Base (BNCC), which defines the set of essential learning that every student has to develop throughout their stages at school.

STUDY CYCLE AS A TRAINING AND COLLABORATIVE ACTIVITY

Faced with the transformations that have taken place in our society, we see that such changes directly affect all sectors, in this case, the school, not being different, where this institution has tried to (re)invent itself and meet the needs that have arisen and develop a work that contributes to the integral formation of the subject. We understand education as a dynamic, social and political practice, capable of favoring the emancipation of subjects. We support

Freire (1978), when he highlights that education cannot be seen as an act of domination, but understood as:

education committed to liberation cannot constitute an understanding of the human as an “empty” being (emphasis added), whom the world “fills” with content [...], but men [and women] as “bodies conscious” and in consciousness as consciousness intended for the world (FREIRE, 1978, p. 77).

In this direction, we believe that this viability of contributing to the process of human emancipation is a challenge for current education, whose purpose is to train critical and reflective students, capable of improving the society in which they live, through dialogue and effective actions. and transformative, in favor of building an education with social quality and based on inclusive and ethical principles.

Faced with this issue, we emphasize that this topic is intended to discuss the importance of the study cycles that were developed as training activities in Pibid Alfabetização of CAP/UERN, whose objective was to favor a space for construction, discussion and expansion of knowledge aimed at the area of teaching, literacy, teacher training and pedagogical practice, these being some of the axes worked on by the subproject, which contribute to the learning of teaching by the undergraduate students participating in the program.

Studies point out that teachers construct their conceptions about teaching from multiple sources of learning (TARDIF; LESSARD, 2005). Our understanding of teaching learning is based on a continuous process, which takes place throughout professional life, articulated with the practices and context of teachers' activity (ANDRÉ, 2010).

The training cycles were characterized by training activities through theoretical studies carried out weekly, on Monday afternoons, with the participation of students participating in the literacy subproject, supervisory teachers of the schools participating in the project and the area coordinator teacher. , in which everyone studies the suggested materials, discusses and seeks to establish a relationship with the teacher's practice, as an alternative for (re)thinking the multiple possibilities of teaching and learning in basic education.

In this way of thinking, text study activities took place weekly, where we discussed a theme focused on teacher identity and professionalism. We also carried out studies of pedagogical works, with different themes, among them: Literacy, reading and writing at school, the National Literacy Policy Document – PNA (Brazil, 2020), didactics and teaching, lesson planning, lesson plans, finally, the themes were intertwined and sought to dialogue with the experiences that guide the classroom, contributing to (re)thinking the school, its challenges and favoring the process of action and reflection in teaching practice.

If, on the one hand, the problems and impasses of the teacher's daily experience are not resolved merely by some postulate external to him, on the other hand, there is a need for a group action-reflection, on the part of the professors, for the understanding of these problems and impasses. It is in this action-reflection interpretation that overcoming may occur. (MIZUKAMI, 1986, p.107).

We found in Mizukami (1986), the need for the school to carry out training activities that can provide opportunities for teachers, coordinators and other members of the institution, situations to reflect on the teaching work, the challenges experienced, and therefore, the importance of planning actions that help in the construction of a quality teaching and learning process, and, in the case of the undergraduate students participating in the CAP/UERN Literacy subproject, in contributing so that these pibidians can learn teaching from a collaborative and dialogic relationship between peers.

From carrying out the activities in the study cycle, we saw the grandeur that it provided to the supervisory teachers, in which they had the opportunity to report their experiences, reflect on their practice and self-assess their pedagogical work, as an alternative for growth. and professional development. About professional development, Day points out that these training practices need to consider the teacher in his entirety, Thus,

Professional development involves all spontaneous learning experiences and consciously planned activities undertaken for the direct or indirect benefit of the individual, group or school and which contribute, through these, to the quality of education in the classroom. It is the process through which teachers, as agents of change, review, renew and broaden, individually or collectively, their commitment to the moral purposes of teaching, critically acquire and develop together with children, youth and peers. , knowledge, skills and emotional intelligence, essential for effective professional reflection, planning and practice, in each of the phases of their professional lives (DAY, 2001, p. 20).

Such consideration indicates the need to consider these training activities as paths that enrich the construction of teaching learning, permeated by personal aspects, motivations, intentions and professional aspects, especially the work and career conditions and the school contexts in which carry out their teaching activities. Marcelo Garcia (2009) enriches this discussion by highlighting that teaching professional development must be understood from the perspective of building a professional identity based on the relationships established between teachers, in which:

It is a construction of the professional self, which evolves throughout their careers. Which can be influenced by school, reforms and political contexts,

and which integrates personal commitment, willingness to learn to teach, beliefs, values, knowledge about the subjects they teach and how they teach them, past experiences, as well as as professional vulnerability itself. (MARCELO, 2009, p. 7)

Given this, it is understood that the construction of the subject in formation is constituted in a professional way through the teaching career, because, categorically, the school is responsible and influence in this process of evolution, in view of the changes that are occurring within the space school for the integralization of the commitment and availability to make the pedagogical practice happen, thus, even with the professional vulnerability, teaching-learning is often built walking in the teacher-student partnership.

From the completion of this cycle of studies, we had the opportunity to dialogue with other colleagues, teachers and thus, discuss about the pedagogical work, the challenges of teaching in a collaborative way, from listening to the other, the experiences built on the school floor and establishing a relationship with the contributions presented by Imbernón (2001, p.43-44), when he highlights that this process of professional development and teaching learning is nurtured by elements, such as: career and working conditions, listing the school as its main locus for discussion and construction of knowledge that overcome the dichotomy between theory and practice.

In these moments of study, we observed that we had the opportunity to build new knowledge necessary for the teaching profession, but there was also the mobilization of knowledge by all those involved in the subproject, as stated by Tardif (2002) when discussing teaching knowledge, and points out that the teacher mobilizes different types of knowledge: the knowledge of professional training, which refers to the sciences of education and pedagogical ideas; disciplinary knowledge, related to specific disciplines; curriculum knowledge, related to dealing with the school program; and experiential knowledge, which is that of individual professional experience and socialization at work. With this, the author also defends the school as a space where the teacher produces specific knowledge that is used by him in his daily work.

In this way, the study cycle was a potentiating activity that helped us to reflect that learning to be a teacher is not a quick activity that has a recipe, but a transforming and challenging process, whose purpose is to allow participants to a path of comings and goings, of reflecting on practice and (re)thinking them. We agree with Imbernón (2001) when he draws our attention to the need for creative teacher training that is capable of responding to the various problem-situations that may occur in the educational routine.

In this vein, we believe that Pibid is a potentiating program and characterized as an initiative that has a strong impact on the debate on the university-school relationship in the

field of teacher training (GATTI et al., 2014; NÓVOA, 2015; FARIAS; JARDILINO; SILVESTRE, 2015), becoming a relevant space for articulating theory and practice in learning the teaching profession by assuming the purpose of “fostering initiation into teaching, contributing to the improvement of teacher education at a higher level and to improving the quality of Brazilian public basic education.” (BRAZIL, Decree No. 7.219/10).

In this perspective, the idea of study cycles developed by Pibid Alfabetização of CAP/UERN, highlighted concerns about the teacher's learning, about how he learns, considering that he is an adult (GARCIA, 1999; MIZUKAMI et al., 2002; NOFFS; RODRIGUES, 2011; PLACCO; SOUZA, 2006). Therefore, we understand that learning:

(...) it means accepting that we don't know everything, or that we know incompletely or imprecisely or even wrongly, which is painful; on the other hand, it is related to the pleasure of discovering, creating, inventing and finding answers for what one is looking for, for the conquest of new knowledge (PLACCO; SOUZA, 2006, p. 20).

Thus, we understand that the teacher learns through processes of socialization and interaction with peers, with students and reflecting on their own practice, as a way of becoming a teacher, in which teaching presents itself as a problem situation to be faced (ARAÚJO, 2003).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGICAL COURSE

The methodology that underlies the following research has a qualitative approach, based on a literature review as a way to deepen theoretically in relation to the theme. Qualitative research, according to Vieira and Zouain (2005) attribute fundamental importance to the testimonies of the social actors involved, to the speeches and the meanings transmitted by them. In relation to the literature review, it is a very important tool, because “[...] it allows the researcher to become aware, in a single source, of what has occurred or is occurring periodically in the field studied, and can replace the consultation of a series from other works. [...]” (NORONHA; FERREIRA, 2000, p. 192). And, of course, it is important to pay attention to the value attributed to the publication so that it actually has quality.

The type of research used allows the application of procedures and instruments to achieve the established objective, and one of these is documentary research as a means of producing new knowledge. To facilitate the understanding of documentary research, we can rely on what Helder (2006:1-2) says: “The documentary technique makes use of original documents, which have not yet received analytical treatment by any author. [...] is one of the

decisive techniques for research in social sciences and humanities”. That is, the documentary technique makes it possible to extract information from documents in order to understand certain issues.

Thus, to answer some of the questions that arise during the research, we used a questionnaire as an instrument that, according to Gil (1999, p.128) can be explained “as the investigation technique composed of a more or less high number of questions. questions presented in writing to people, with the objective of knowing opinions, beliefs, feelings, interests, expectations, situations experienced, etc.”. Based on these questions, a questionnaire was prepared containing four discursive questions about the researched theme and, then, the questions were sent to two supervisory teachers of PIBID Alfabetização of CAP/UERN, in order to better understand the perspective of each one on the program.

DATA ANALYSIS

An interview was conducted with the two supervising teachers of the Literacy subproject - PIBID, through a questionnaire via Whatsapp. For ethical reasons, we will name the teachers as P1, kindergarten teacher, and P2, as a teacher of the early years of elementary school, respectively. We started the dialogue based on the following reflection: It is known that teaching construction is a continuous process and that it constantly requires innovations regarding the methods that influence the learning process to take place. When asked about what it would take to act as a teacher, they replied:

Training in the area of pedagogy or in various degrees, dedication, patience and love is required. (P1)

Being a teacher, it is not enough to take a pedagogy course, being a teacher, primarily he needs to know if he wants to be a teacher, that is, within the course you chose, you will go through an internship, for example, pedagogy and you, in the period of your internship, you will know what it is to be a teacher, what it is to teach, being a teacher is not just teaching, it is a much more arduous mission, so being a teacher is primarily having love for the profession, commitment and dedication, whatever grade you yes, if you don't have these three obstacles, you didn't turn out to be a good professional and today being a teacher is not just any way, being a teacher, you have to dedicate yourself, in every profession but in my point of view, the teacher is more, the teacher, he will form opinions, he will use strategies to be an opinion former, so he has to be very careful with what he is going to do and why he is going to do it, for whom he is going to do it and for whom he is going to do it, so, being a teacher, just training in pedagogy is not enough, it is not enough just a pedagogy course to be a teacher, I have to dedicate myself to being a teacher. (P2)

We can see from P1's answer that it is necessary to have training in the degree course in Pedagogy, but that alone is not enough, dedication, patience, love and commitment to teaching is required. The teacher's words remind us of what Paulo Freire (1987) says in *Pedagogy of the Oppressed* about loveliness in education. According to Freire, "education is an act of love", in which men and women who recognize themselves as unfinished beings are, therefore, as beings capable of learning. On the contrary, if there is no dialogue, there is no deep love for the world and men.

Meanwhile, P2 argues that to become a teacher it is important to know if it is really what the subject, in the process of his formation, aspires to be. Not being enough, therefore, just to have a diploma or, it is not enough just to teach, it is necessary to have love for the profession. Here we can quote what Rubem Alves says when pronouncing the distinction between teacher and educator, when he states that, "a teacher is a profession, it is not something that is defined from within, out of love. Educator, on the contrary, is not a profession; it is vocation. And every vocation is born of great love, of great hope." (Apud FERACINE, 1998, p.50). In addition, the interviewee highlights the importance of the internship to discover herself in the profession and says that there are three crucial points to become a good teacher, which are: love, commitment and dedication. Furthermore, one cannot be a teacher without planning, one must use strategies and be careful, since the teacher helps in this initial process of forming the child's reflective thinking.

About the training meetings held during our subproject - Literacy, we asked the teachers about the main contributions they provided to their teaching practice. Both highlight:

Exchange of information and ideas with participants, knowledge using theory and practice, rethinking and evaluating my practice based on discussions and exchange of ideas. (P1)

It is extremely important, it is where you will learn from the other, the teacher, that is, in any profession, he does not learn alone, the exchange of experiences, the day to day, each one with different realities, so these exchanges, these contributions, continuing education with the contributions that we are adapting to our reality on a day-to-day basis, so it is of paramount importance for teaching practice. (P2)

From the answers, we see that P1 focuses on the importance of having an exchange of ideas and experiences between the participants and from the discussions, using the knowledge for a reflective practice, following the theories. We resort, therefore, to the conception of Freire (2013), when he states that theory and practice are inseparable, becoming, through their relationship, authentic praxis, which enables subjects to reflect on action, providing education

for freedom . "Praxis, however, is the reflection and action of men on the world in order to transform it".

Interviewee P2, in turn, makes similar highlights and emphasizes the importance of the meetings, the exchange of contributions, the importance of experiencing the day-to-day life of a classroom, thus being able to put into practice the reflections of the meetings (reflect, practice and reflect) experiencing the cycle of continuing education that a teacher needs to achieve a higher success rate. Continuing training is necessary, therefore, since, according to Nóvoa (1995), teachers encounter situations with unified characteristics, for this reason, it requires unified solutions, and initial training does not take into account, aiming at specific discussions of the reality of each educational space.

Analyzing the opportunity that PIBID provides at the beginning of teacher training, that is, experiencing this first contact in the classroom, thus reflecting on theories and practices, we question the importance of reflecting on teaching practice at the university. The teachers replied:

That each professional is committed to his work, deepening his knowledge, since he is a reproducer and transmitter of knowledge, deepening his knowledge and qualifying not only in his specific area. (P1)

Many, it gives us many reflections, we observe that we participate in many wonderful meetings, that we learn by doing, we learn from this exchange of experiences, teacher and teacher, teacher and student, student and teacher, student and student, so, this exchange of experience is fundamental for teacher education. (P2)

Through the discussions presented, we noticed that P1 focuses on the commitment to teaching that every teacher needs to be always looking to improve their methodologies and knowledge, since the teacher is a social mirror and one of the central educational pillars. We then carried out a notoriety for the planning. According to Libâneo (1994), planning has great relevance as it is part of a process of rationalization, organization and coordination of teaching action, where it articulates school activities with situations in the social context.

However, P2 highlights the moments of reflection that the meetings provide, where teachers learn from each other, from students, and that, students, learn from their own experiences, carrying out reflections and exchanges of experiences that are fundamental in the formation of a teacher. Siqueira (2011), attests to the affinity between the teacher and the student, being a pleasant, motivating and interesting factor for learning. It also serves as an aid tool to reach the student's attention and promote the development of more meaningful learning by facilitating this process and empowering him as a human being.

The training meetings of our subproject, due to the Covid-19 pandemic, were held weekly in a remote format. However, it did not diminish the quality of the works developed, which provided unique moments that would be practically unlikely in person. When asked about the importance of training meetings, they highlighted:

Encourage and qualify training, providing the chance to be excellent professionals, contributing to the articulation between theory and practice. (P1)

I always tell you that when I finish a PIBID training with you, I finish with a bag full. The PIBID formative meetings are very important, it is where we observe when that student wants to be a teacher, it is where we observe the exchange of experiences lived by the pibidians in the classroom, it is an inexplicable experience, these formative meetings are very important from PIBID, we have good lectures, good activities presented, many works of extreme relevance that we adapt to our classroom, to our practice, the teacher (I shoot for myself) I learn a lot with these PIBID formations, an exchange of experiences that there's no way for us, if you say like this: I'm not going to participate in this PIBID training, I'm not capable of saying that. I learn a lot with PIBID, with the exchange of experience, with thinkers, with the discussions between us (coordinators, supervisors and pibidians) so the formation of PIBID meetings is extremely important. (P2)

As he points out, P1 responds to the question citing the importance of encouraging the qualification of the training that the program provides, so professionals will have a greater articulation between theory and practice, increasing the chances of students to be excellent professionals. In this way, we commit ourselves to what Dias (2009) says, in this context, that knowledge can evolve according to the search for specializations of practices, as the job market expands and requires professionals with specialized qualifications. In addition, education is committed to motivating the social status and development of the country.

On the other hand, we noticed that P2 reports that despite the many experiences he had with previous programs, he always ends the training with a full "baggage". Regardless of her experiences, she says that she always learns a lot from each one, and considers PIBID a very rich program, of great relevance. Each training event, lectures, study cycles contribute and provide opportunities for teaching action and reflection on their practice. Finally, she stresses that she is very grateful to be part of the program.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The general objective of this study was to reflect on the contributions of study cycles as a teaching activity with PIBID graduates from the perspective of teaching initiation, carried out in this pandemic context, remotely.

From the literature review and document analysis carried out, we evidenced the importance of study cycles as a formative activity that facilitated the construction of knowledge about themes related to teaching learning, literacy and literacy, childhood, playfulness, and finally, the teacher's pedagogical practice both in kindergarten and in the early years of elementary school.

The findings of this investigation, collected through a questionnaire applied to the teachers, point out that the training cycles carried out during the subproject were affluent to a teaching practice linked to theory. However, theory cannot be just talk, as this is the beginning of a (re)thinking of practice. In the conception of Paulo Freire (2013), theory and practice are inseparable, becoming, through their relationship, authentic praxis, which enables subjects to reflect on action, providing education for freedom.

We conclude, therefore, paying attention to one more relevant factor of the cycle, which is the act of contributing to the other, whether student or teacher. From the study cycle, we understand that each one has speeches and practices that can and will contribute both to the formation and professional growth of the other. In addition, the training cycles contributed significantly to thinking about practice in Basic Education schools. In the face of the pandemic context, the chances of relating theory to practice in an appropriate way, that is, acting in the classroom, was not possible. However, the exchanges of experiences built from the moments of study were unique and essential to contribute to the reflective exercise of the participants, giving them the opportunity to relate the theories studied with the practice developed in the classroom, thus favoring a continuous (re)thinking about teaching learning.

REFERENCES

DAYS. Maria Jose Pereira de Oliveira. **Challenges and perspectives of teachers in the training process** . Goiania, 2009.

FERACINE, Luiz. **The teacher as an agent of social change** . São Paulo: EPU, 1990.

FREIRE, Paul. **Pedagogy of the Oppressed** . 17. ed. Rio de Janeiro: Peace and Land, 1987.

—. **Pedagogy of the Oppressed** . 54. ed. 2013.

GILL, Antonio Carlos. **Social research methods and techniques** . 5. ed. São Paulo: Atlas, 1999.

Helder, R. 2006. **How to do document analysis** . Porto, University of Algarve.

LIBÂNEO, Jose Carlos. Didactics - São Paulo: Cortez, 1994 (Second degree teaching collection. Teacher training).

MORIN, Edgar. **La Voie: pour l'avenir de l'humanité** . Paris: Fayard, 2011. NORONHA, Daisy Pires; FERREIRA, Sueli Mara SP Literature reviews. In: CAMPELLO, Bernadette Santos; CONDÓN, Beatriz Valadares; KREMER, Jeannette Marguerite (eds.) **Sources of information for researchers and practitioners** . Belo Horizonte: UFMG, 2000.

NEW, Antonio. (Org.). **Teachers' Lives**. Portugal: Porto, 1995.

LARGE NORTHERN RIVER. **Literacy Subproject** . PIBID CAP/UERN. 2020.

SIQUEIRA, Alessandra Maria de Oliveira; NETO, Demuniz Diniz da Silva; FLORENCE, Ruthmara. **The Importance of Affection in Student Learning, Faculty of Sciences, Education and Theology of Northern Brazil** . 2011.

VIEIRA, MMF and ZOUAIN, DM **Qualitative research in administration: theory and practice** . Rio de Janeiro: Editora FGV, 2005.